

Assessment and Demonstration

Life Cycle Assessment

Environmental Life cycle Assessment (LCA) is a methodology to assess all the environmental impacts of a product or a service during the whole life cycle from the raw material extraction to final disposal. In Switzerland, the use of coloured PV façades has become popular due to improved visual acceptance. At the same time, life cycle assessment of buildings becomes increasingly important. While a life cycle inventory for conventional glass-film PV laminates is available, this is not the case for glass-glass laminates, and in particular, coloured front glasses.

A study [1] was conducted with industrial partners to assess the environmental impact of multicoloured glass-glass laminates in terms of Swiss eco-points, cumulative energy demand (CED), and global warming potential (GWP). To this end, a hypothetical façade installation comparing its energy payback time (EPBT) compared to that of the Swiss low-voltage electricity grid as reference. In a further study [2], this analysis was also applied to a novel lightweight PV laminate designed to reduce roof loading.

Keywords: coloured glass; life cycle assessment; building integrated photovoltaics; LCA; LCI; BIPV

Target audience: Architects, planners, and their clients

Multi-Coloured Glass-Glass PV Laminates

To realistically assess the environmental impact of the entire life cycle of a multi-coloured glass-glass PV laminate, material and energy flow data was obtained from a solar glass and PV laminate supplier, and quantified in terms of impact metrics. The figure below shows the environmental impact of multi-coloured glass production using a digital ceramic printing process for a PV laminate of size ca. 1.16 m², expressed in eco-points (kPt). To encompass the entire life cycle of a PV laminate, the study considered a façade installation consisting of 140 laminates.

Using multi-coloured glass-glass laminates instead of clear solar glass decreases energy production by 20%, reducing the façade's capacity to 24.6 kWp. In terms of ecological impact, this incurs a negligible 0.1% increase in eco-points for the digital ceramic printing, but a significant 4% and 20% increase due to additional glass and reduced electricity yield, respectively.

The figure below show the CED vs. EPBT of a multicoloured PV façade with various orientations over a projected 30-year operational lifespan compared to that of the Swiss low-voltage electricity grid as reference. An optimal EPBT of 8.1 years is obtained with a south-facing orientation, which can be reduced to 5.3 years when replacing the glass rain cladding in an existing façade. This compares favourably with the reference 6.7 years and leaves ca. 25 years for surplus electricity production.

Lightweight (<6 kg/m²) PV laminates replace the rear glass with a composite sandwich consisting of an aluminium honeycomb core and fibreglass reinforced polymers. The polymers increase the GWP of a lightweight PV façade by 10% compared to one using glass-glass laminates. This results in a ca. 2% increase in CED, but the corresponding EPBT of 6.7 years is comparable with that of both glass-glass laminates and the reference Swiss low-voltage electricity grid (see figure below).

References

- [1] Jeeyoung Park, Dirk Hengevoss, Stephen Wittkopf. **Industrial Data-Based Life Cycle Assessment of Architecturally Integrated Glass-Glass Photovoltaics**. *Buildings* 2019, 9(1), 8; <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings9010008>
- [2] Jeeyoung Park, Dirk Hengevoss, Stephen Wittkopf. **Life Cycle Assessment of Novel Lightweight Rigid BIPV Technology in an Early Design and Research Phase**. Technical Report, Jan. 2018. <https://www.zenodo.org/record/2546647>